

Title page

Neighbourhood food stories: a secondary analysis across five years of data identifying food practices in a community facing financial constraints

Authors

Bramble H Gardiner¹, Lorna Zischka¹, Sally Lloyd-Evans¹, Lisa Methven², Carol Wagstaff²

Affiliations

1. Department of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Reading (UK) *Geography Building, University of Reading, Whiteknights, PO Box 227, Reading, RG6 6AB*
2. Department of Food and Nutritional Sciences, University of Reading (UK) *Harry Nursten Building, University of Reading, Whiteknights, Reading, RG6 6DZ*

Biographies

Bramble Gardiner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2246-8320>

Bramble is a Research Assistant at the University of Reading and a PhD student at the University of Plymouth. They specialise in creative and participatory methods, with recent work focusing on food justice and food system transformation. Their academic work builds on previous experience in innovation and the third sector, including socially engaged art, citizen science, alternative governance, community ownership, and surplus food distribution. Bramble is passionate about working towards climate justice, social justice, and a world where all beings on the planet can have a good life.

Lorna Zischka <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7895-9268>

Dr Lorna Zischka is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the University of Reading. She works with the Participatory Action Research team, particularly in data analysis. Her interests lie in poverty alleviation and social justice, and she worked with development NGOs for over a decade before pursuing these interests at the University of Reading. Lorna's research into the central role of interpersonal relationships on community outcomes can be read in her book, '[Giving behaviours and social cohesion: How people who 'give' make better communities.](#)'

Sally Lloyd-Evans <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4234-4269>

Sally is an Associate Professor in of human geography. She particularly specialises in participatory and co-produced methods, with research interests including Geographies of Development, Social Inequalities and Work. Since 2014 she has led Participatory Action Research (PAR) programmes with community and public sector organisations tackling social and health inequalities across SE England and a community research collective called the 'Whitley Researchers'. In 2020 she became the first holder of a Public Engagement with Community Research fellowship at the University of Reading and

recently led the UKRI Community Led Research Pilot in partnership with the British Science Association and an NHS Community Participatory Action Research (CPAR) programme on health inequalities.

Lisa Methven <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6940-7579>

Lisa is a Professor of Food and Nutritional Sciences at the University of Reading. Her particular areas of expertise is food sensory science. Her research investigates causes and influences of individual differences in sensory perception and how they impact food preferences. Lisa is involved in co-creating solutions with people, focusing on achieving healthier desirable diets for all ages and all communities.

Carol Wagstaff <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9400-8641>

Carol is a Professor at the University of Reading, with specialisms across food system topics. She is particularly interested in developing a food system that addresses food inequities, so that everyone can access a culturally appropriate, healthy, sustainable, affordable and enjoyable diet. She has also performed significant work towards improving the quality of horticultural crops, including the nutritional value, appearance, flavour and shelf life, in order to support consumers in making healthy dietary choices. She was the Principal Investigator of Food Systems Equality (FoodSEqual), funded by the UKRI Strategic Priorities fund during 2021-2025.

Corresponding author:

Bramble Gardiner

b.h.gardiner@reading.ac.uk

Geography Building, University of Reading, Whiteknights, PO Box 227, Reading, RG6 6AB

WORD COUNT (with tables, figure headings and footnotes; but without references): **10590**

WORD COUNT (without tables, figure headings, footnotes, or references): **8488**

1 Abstract [300 words]

2 Diet inequalities are one of many social determinants of poor health disproportionately
3 affecting low-income communities. FoodSEqual (the Food Systems Equality consortium)
4 worked across four such communities from 2021-2025, aiming to co-produce changes to
5 reduce food system inequalities. Most outputs had specific purposes (e.g. policy, products)
6 and harnessed specific parts of the data. Our secondary analysis looks across the rich
7 lived/living experiences documented in one location (Whitley, Reading). Following
8 participatory values, we also report participants' proposals for change. Our qualitative
9 content analysis used an *a priori* approach, applying social practice theory to identify 'nexus
10 practices' which sit at the intersection of many others. The analysis illustrates the utility of
11 shifting thinking from 'health behaviours' to 'health practices' and using mixed methods
12 which integrate lived/living experience to identify targeted food environment interventions.

13
14 The most connected nexus practice was 'managing financial constraints'; broad impacts
15 from low or unpredictable incomes include choosing long-life foods to avoid waste and
16 navigate financial instability. Participants proposed upstream and 'sideways' interventions
17 like improving wages and routes to work alongside targeted cash or voucher assistance. The
18 next most connected practice was 'a need for moments of ease', an alternative intervention
19 focus than 'convenience' which recognises inequalities of ease accompany low incomes. The
20 third most connected was 'selective children influencing household foods', varied reasons
21 included sensory issues and familiarity with only a narrow range of foods. This could be
22 addressed via community-based and regulatory interventions. 'Managing wellbeing' had the
23 most competing connections, with broader wellbeing needs sometimes prioritised over
24 nutrition. Experiences and impacts of stigma were evident, impacting wellbeing. Community
25 feedback further emphasised physical access. This is influenced by life circumstances,
26 requiring targeted interventions. We conclude food environment interventions must
27 address stigma and go beyond food to reduce financial constraints and identify how to meet
28 needs for wellbeing and ease.

29 30 **Keywords**

31 Diet inequalities, social determinants, food environments, food practices, wellbeing, lived
32 experience, upstream interventions

33

34 1. Introduction

35 Our research is firmly rooted in the need to understand and consider the 'full picture of
36 people's realities', as proposed by the Director of Agrifood Systems at FAO (Hawkes et al.,
37 2024), in order to enable successful food environment policies and interventions. This article
38 aims to contribute to addressing preconceptions and assumptions about the choices made
39 by people managing life on low incomes.

40 **1.1. Diet and health inequalities in context**

41 Diet is the leading cause of avoidable ill health across the UK population (Food Standards
42 Agency, 2022; Goddard, 2025). However, food consumption patterns in the UK are highly
43 correlated with income; for example, purchases of fruit and vegetables increase when
44 people have higher incomes (DEFRA, 2024). The Food Foundation (2025) estimate that to
45 meet diet recommendations “the most deprived fifth of the population would need to spend
46 45% of their disposable income on food, rising to 70% for those households with children”
47 (p.1). Supporting people to meet Eatwell Guide recommendations would benefit population
48 health (Scheelbeek et al., 2020), and many healthier foods are also associated with less
49 environmental impacts (Scheelbeek et al., 2020, 2023).

50 Beyond affording a healthy diet, some experience food insecurity, struggling to access food
51 consistently or at all, with recent food price inflation exacerbating household food insecurity
52 globally (FAO et al., 2025). The current cost of living crisis in the UK has further increased the
53 already high numbers of people accessing emergency food aid (EFRA, 2023; DEFRA, 2024).
54 Risks of further instability in UK fruit and vegetable supplies from climate change impacts
55 have been predicted (Scheelbeek et al., 2023). There are also feedback loops where poor
56 health influences diet outcomes, which in turn influence health (Puddephatt et al., 2020;
57 Hunt et al., 2023). Additionally, those with disabilities are among those most at risk of
58 experiencing food insecurity (Loopstra, 2020).

59 Notably, there is long-standing stigma surrounding having a low income (Tyler and Campbell,
60 2024). This includes false but pervasive public narratives about ‘cultures of worklessness’ or
61 personal failure (Pemberton et al., 2016). These intersect with unhelpful ‘blame and shame’
62 responses to diet-related health conditions (Browne et al., 2013; Duarte et al., 2017; Hunter
63 et al., 2025), which can enter into policies and policy narratives (Griffin et al., 2021).

64 The majority of barriers or facilitators to healthy eating are suggested to relate to
65 environmental context and resources, including physical accessibility of different foods,
66 living circumstances, and experiences while growing up (Briazu et al., 2024). These are all
67 influenced by area-based and socioeconomic inequalities which also impact UK residents
68 health and life expectancy (Marmot et al., 2020; OHID, 2022); the social determinants of
69 health (OHID, 2025). This affirms the need to move beyond individual behaviours to consider
70 contextual factors. Concepts used for exploring such dynamics include the ‘food
71 environment’ (Story et al., 2008), which has gained policy attention (DEFRA, 2024).

72 However, food environment research is critiqued for insufficiently considering the cultural
73 aspects of food (Araújo et al., 2022) and the emergent relational nature of food
74 environments (López Cifuentes and Sonnino, 2024). Methodological limitations of food
75 environments research have also been discussed (Lucan, 2015; Sacks et al., 2019). Important
76 considerations for food environment analyses include people’s perceptions alongside
77 material, physical and political dimensions (Vonthron et al., 2020). One theoretical

78 framework proposed to support such analyses is social practice theory (Mattioni et al., 2020;
79 Vonthron et al., 2020), which our research applies.

80 **1.2. Health behaviours to health practices**

81 With the rise of ‘lifestyle’ linked diseases the concept of ‘health behaviours’ arose (e.g.
82 OHID, 2022) – with assumptions that distinct universal health behaviours with causal
83 explanations can be identified and changed (Cohn, 2014). This is critiqued as insufficient to
84 explain complex human behaviours and for focusing on individual responsibility, leading to
85 interventions that ignore complex structural factors influencing health (Cohn, 2014); which
86 are known to be impactful (Marmot et al., 2020). Nonetheless, structural factors such as
87 social determinants do not *determine* health outcomes, only risk factors (Lundberg, 2020).
88 Individuals have (constrained and situated) agency and act in heterogeneous ways
89 (Lundberg, 2020). Thus, practice theory and the idea of ‘health practices’ offer opportunities
90 to better explain ‘conditioned’ agency in everyday life, where people act within material or
91 normative constraints (Delormier et al., 2009; Cohn, 2014; Warde, 2014; Halkier and Holm,
92 2021). Analysing practices can also enable exploration of the social micro-processes involved
93 in the links between nutrient-poor diets and social disadvantage (Halkier and Holm, 2021).
94 Here, we aim to illustrate how the application of social practice theory can support efforts to
95 transform food environments and food system inequities.

96

97 **1.3. Social practice theory**

98 We draw from Shove et al. (2012) to describe social practices as routinised activities
99 performed across daily life. Practices are initially distinguished as organized entities at a
100 societal level (practice-as-entity), with spatial and temporal elements categorised as
101 materials, meaning and competencies¹. These elements come together in individual
102 performances of practices in specific contexts (practice-as-performances) which are
103 recognisable everyday activities, such as cooking a specific food in a specific kitchen. These
104 two practices have a recursive relationship in which practices-as-entities are reproduced
105 through repeated performances, and the performance of practices is guided by the
106 elements entangled within practices-as-entities (Shove et al., 2012). Practices are also
107 influenced by broader societal organisation and context, and in turn through their repetition
108 create and influence societal organisation (Shove et al., 2012; Castelo et al., 2021). As
109 performances are not practiced ‘perfectly’, recursive performances of practices
110 incorporating small adaptations can lead to change (Shove et al., 2012).

¹ Castelo et al., (2021) highlight varied subcategories under these three broad categories: material (things, technologies, infrastructures), competence (skills, know-how and techniques), meaning (how people make sense of their actions, and what motivates them). Shove herself recognises these as ‘slippery’ categories (Shove et al., 2012), however we will work with them as useful analytical categories particularly as integrated into an analysis framework by Castelo et al. (2021).

111 Practices tend to be networked together, and their interconnections can be collaborative or
112 competitive (i.e. they compete, reinforce, hybridise, cross-reference or colonise each other)
113 (Shove et al., 2012; Castelo et al., 2021). For example, eating a biscuit whilst drinking a
114 coffee could be considered practices reinforcing each other - both being associated with
115 having a break. Our work responds to suggestions that interconnections within networks of
116 practices are insufficiently explored, and are significant in understanding how practices
117 might change (Castelo et al., 2021). We focus on ‘nexus practices’, these sit at the
118 intersection of many others and can offer “a deeper understanding of why certain practices
119 are carried out in the way they are” (Castelo et al., 2021, p. 6).

120 **1.4. Food practices**

121 We took ‘food practices’ as our unit of analysis, which included complex inter-related
122 practices, such as shopping, transporting, cooking and eating; recognising that these
123 activities may share constituent elements (e.g. the meaning ‘being healthy’ could be a
124 common touchpoint between shopping, eating, and exercising) (Castelo et al., 2021). Hence
125 food practices function as ‘networks of practices’, and are entangled with other practices
126 such as working or parenting (Castelo et al., 2021).

127 Cultural notions of appropriate eating behaviour vary across geographic locations, social
128 groups, over time and in specific contexts; for example “eating leftovers” may be less
129 acceptable in a group setting than when eating alone (Castelo et al., 2021; Halkier and Holm,
130 2021). Eating is also affected by distribution and production practices, with wider influences
131 including regulation, trade, and governance (Castelo et al., 2021). We adapted Castelo et
132 al.’s (2021) framework to analyse networks of food practices and situate them as examples
133 of food practices among a specific group of people in a specific place at a specific time. The
134 embedding of food practices in social contexts has significant influence (Delormier et al.,
135 2009; Isaacs et al., 2022), so should be included in practice analyses (Castelo et al., 2021).
136 Analysing at neighbourhood level is useful given spatial dimensions of inequalities (Mudie et
137 al., 2025), and can help catalyse change starting from a neighbourhood scale (Russell and
138 McKnight, 2022). Additionally, consideration of the wider context was undertaken to situate
139 this local scale among wider socio-economic and historical forces and trends.

140 **2. Methods**

141 We aimed to identify the networks of people’s everyday food practices in Whitley (Reading,
142 UK) (Box 1) and explore contextual influences on these networks. Aligning with participatory
143 values (Leask et al., 2019), we also honour proposals for change participants made
144 themselves. This article was informed by quality standards for reporting qualitative research
145 (O’Brien et al., 2014).

146 **2.1. Secondary data analysis**

147 This is a secondary analysis of data produced during FoodSEqual (2021-2025)
148 (<https://research.reading.ac.uk/food-systems-equality/>). The primary research aimed to co-
149 produce food products and policy changes to reduce food system inequalities (Wagstaff et

150 al., 2025). FoodSEqual was co-delivered with community partners in community settings and
 151 local community researchers to foreground lived experiences and stories (Pettinger et al.,
 152 2023). We deliver a supplementary analysis (Heaton, 2012), extending beyond a focus on
 153 product and policy innovation to tell the story of people’s food practices and how these
 154 integrate across their lives.

155 In qualitative research, because data are co-constructed with participants, there are
 156 implications of reusing data out of context (Irwin, 2013). However, all co-authors were
 157 involved in FoodSEqual and remained embedded in the context throughout the secondary
 158 analysis. Therefore, there was minimal need to ‘(re)contextualise’ and ‘(re)connect’ the data
 159 (Kahryn Hughes, 2023), except in epistemological terms.

160 We worked with a convenience sample, using data available to the community research
 161 team in Whitley (this includes community researchers, one postdoctoral researcher, one
 162 community coordinator and one lead academic). Almost all data are from studies led by
 163 them, some were co-led with cross-disciplinary food scientists from psychologists to food
 164 technologists (Table 1). Our secondary analysis is situated within critical social sciences and
 165 based on social justice values. Potential for bias from the primary study design was
 166 considered during analysis. Detailed demographic data were not collected consistently
 167 across the multiple studies in the primary research; so are not analysed or reported here.
 168 However, all FoodSEqual participants either lived in or were connected to Whitley; the
 169 majority were white British and female, and ages ranged from 20-80. During FoodSEqual’s
 170 delivery, data from each study were summarised into key findings which included large
 171 numbers of quotes. This secondary analysis worked from these summaries and was
 172 informed by iterative dialogue with locally embedded actors (e.g. local residents and
 173 community hub workers) and coauthors involved in the original data collection. This went
 174 beyond ‘member checking’, aiming for ‘reflexive participant collaboration’ (Motulsky, 2021).
 175 Results were also validated by comparing with quantitative surveying from FoodSEqual’s
 176 delivery, this is integrated in the reporting.

177 Table 1: Summarised data from the following research activities were analysed. The person
 178 who summarised the data is a coauthor (LZ). Unless indicated otherwise, all participants
 179 were Whitley residents.

	Methods and question investigated	Number of participants	Who led	When delivered
(A)	Structured interviews on what people eat and why	60	Community team (with input from FoodSEqual’s food science and psychology team)	November 2021
(B)	A series of workshops looking into what people eat and why, and what they might want to change.	30+	Co-led by the Community team and FoodSEqual’s food science and psychology team	February – April 2022
(C)	Three separate short follow-up questionnaires to gain more detail about specific foods eaten, including: jarred	75	Community team (with input from FoodSEqual’s food science team)	April-May 2022

	foods; consumption of meat/meat alternatives; consumption of takeaways			
(D)	This was followed up by a further workshop at the university which involved academics, industry stakeholders and community researchers and a short questionnaire to help with ranking ideas from studies (B) and (C)	22 community members, 6 industrial partners, 25 academics 15	FoodSEqual's food science team Community team	May 2022
(E)	Interviews of people obtaining food support, looking at barriers and what works best.	29	Community team	July 2022
(F)	Two workshops and discussing the cost-of-living crisis plus multiple planning and reflection sessions	26 (including 6 community researchers)	Community team	January - February 2023
(G)	A questionnaire asking parents (mostly mothers) to share their experiences of getting children to eat fruit and veg and what they think might help them improve intake	42	Community team	October 2023
(H)	Reflections on personal experience of getting children to eat fruit and veg	7 (female) community researchers	Community team	October 2023
(I)	4 workshops on issues to do with vegetables. The themes of the workshops were selected following a prioritisation vote involving 13 participants. Two workshops focused on organic veg and growing your own, and two on obtaining fresh and processed veg via food support.	20	Co-led by the Community team and FoodSEqual's food science and psychology team	January 2024
(J)	Community feedback on findings at a community event	32	Community team (with input from FoodSEqual's food science team)	April 2024
(K)	A questionnaire exploring what people like or don't like about their diets and shopping, barriers to change, and priorities for action and food system change	72	Community team	September 2024

180

181 Box 1: a brief profile of the case study location

Area profile: The area popularly referred to as 'Whitley' in South Reading (UK) comprises parts Whitley Ward and parts of Church Ward. Ranked by the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD), this area was historically the most deprived in Reading, some parts ranking in the bottom 10% most deprived in the UK (MHCLG, 2015). Whitley's reputation has suffered from a long-term association with social deprivation, and this sense of stigmatisation lingers despite recent improvements in IMD rankings (MHCLG, 2025). Some areas of Whitley still fall into the 20% most deprived in the UK, including the health deprivation and disability domain (measuring risk of premature death and impaired quality of life because of poor physical and mental health) (Reading Borough Council, 2025).

182

183 2.2. Analysis of Food Practices

184 This qualitative content analysis (Schreier, 2014) took an *a priori* approach to identify
185 ‘expressions’ of themes relevant to pre-selected theoretical concepts (Ryan and Bernard,
186 2003). The coding approach was inductive subsumption (Schreier, 2014); identifying
187 material appropriate to the categories of interest, expanding categories with sub-codes, and
188 identifying if additional categories were needed. Analysis focused on the explicit ideas
189 described in the text and how they related to the chosen theoretical concepts, with the
190 categories primarily functioning at the descriptive level of text and participants’ explicit
191 accounts (Vaismoradi et al., 2016).

192 The analysis process and coding framework were adapted from Castelo et al. (2021) (Table
193 2). We used the coding function of NVivo (Lumivero, 2023) to categorise practices and their
194 elements (materials, meanings, competencies) (step 2) and any contextual influences
195 discussed (step 4); and the relationship function to capture network categories (step 3).
196 Nexus practices were identified by downloading a spreadsheet to identify codes (practices)
197 with the highest number of relationships (nexus practices) and to identify those with the
198 most competitive relationships. NVivo’s ‘mapping’ function was used to explore nexus
199 practice connections. Contextual factors reported were identified in the data, then
200 expanded using academic literature.

201 We varied from Castelo et al. (2021) as follows: (i) We did not look for ‘internal variation’ of
202 practices based on spatial or temporal location as we examined practices in one particular
203 place, at one particular time, with one particular group of; (ii) We chose food practices as
204 our initial unit of analysis, rather than specifying a single practice such as eating; (iii) We did
205 not analyse the ‘context’ categories in-depth due to the broadness of our initial unit of
206 analysis and time constraints.

Table 2: Coding framework used for each analysis step, adapted from Castelo et al. (2021) to be suited to our research design. Detailed analysis steps are in the supplementary materials.

Step	Higher-level category	Sub-categories and relationship types
1	Identified a unit of analysis as ' Food Practices '	
2	Food Practices 'Zooming in' on Food Practices	Sub-categories comprise the elements from which the practice emerges: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material (things, technologies, infrastructures) • Meaning (motivation, understanding - how people make sense of their actions) • Competence (skills, know-how and techniques)
	Non-food Practices These include practices likely to be inter-related such as money management, parenting etc...	
3	Complex of practices "Complexes of practices describe very close connections between different practices in a 'sticky' way, often including the necessity of co-existence" (Castelo et al., 2021)	These were assigned as relationship types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequence • Co-dependency • Sharing elements
	Bundles of practices "Practices can be loosely connected to each other in bundles – not being entirely, strictly or necessarily co-dependent on each other" (Castelo et al., 2021)	These were assigned as relationship types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-location • Competition • Elements that are shared but not co-dependent (labelled as 'Associated')
	Nexus of practices "A nexus describes indirect connections beyond complexes and bundles. It involves connections between 'seemingly unrelated' practices via practices that intersect with different practices (e.g. mobility practices)" (Castelo et al., 2021, p. 8)	These were identified during relationship modelling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking between several bundles or complexes of practices • Not necessarily sharing elements
4	Wider contextual influences (zooming out) "The influencing context may be related to global trends (e.g. individualisation, globalisation, division of labour), social norms (e.g. being a responsible parent) and cultural specifics (e.g. high value of certain foods)" (Castelo et al., 2021, p. 9).	High-level categories used during the coding included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market-corporate influences - Political-legal influences - Third sector influences - Socio-cultural influences Identification of contextual influences discussed in the data was expanded with points from academic literature.

3. Networks of food practices

Figure 1 shows the nexus and competitive practices identified in our analysis. Three related to non-food ‘practice-as-entities’: money management, health management, and parenting or caring. Other non-food ‘practice-as-entities’ identified as connected to food practices included: communication, community, democratic, domestic management, education, health management, mobility, money management, sustainable living, and working.

Figure 1: Relationships between nexus and competitive practices identified from the analysis of food practices in a community facing financial constraints. Note: contextual influences are important and lacking in this diagram.

3.1. Nexus practices

The top nexus practices were managing financial constraints, the need for moments of ease, and the influence of children who are selective eaters for various reasons (Table 3). Feedback from locally embedded actors was positive, but suggested that physical accessibility of food was missing. Re-examining the analysis revealed that accessibility affected participants differently. This itself is a useful finding, as discussed later.

Table 3: Practices with most connections-relationships

Parent code	Practice	Practice type	Connections (n)
Money management practices	Managing financial constraints	Competency (skill)	25

Cooking practices	A need for moments of ease (little time, lots of stress, need convenience)	Meaning (Motivation)	21
Meaning (motivation): taste, texture and visual appeal	'Selective' children (a strong influence on household choices)	Material (thing)	17
Eating practices	Food as a source of health	Meaning (Motivation)	16
Eating practices	Allergies or dietary restrictions	Material (thing)	13
Health management practices	Managing wellbeing	Competency (skill)	13
Eating practices	Having choice is desirable	Meaning (Motivation)	12
Eating practices	Taste, texture and visual appeal	Meaning (Motivation)	12
Material (thing): cost of food	Cost effectiveness a big influence on choice	Meaning (Motivation)	12
Material (thing): home-cooked food	Home-cooked food is good, healthy food	Meaning (Motivation)	10
Cooking practices	Pre-processed foods	Material (thing)	10
Eating practices	Food as a source of comfort and pleasure	Meaning (Motivation)	10
Meaning (motivation): food as a source of health	Additives and chemicals are unhealthy	Meaning (understanding)	10
Eating practices	High quality food is desirable	Meaning (Motivation)	10
Eating practices	Sharing a meal with others (in a family or elsewhere)	Meaning (Motivation)	10

3.1.1. Money management practices: managing financial constraints

“The healthier you try and eat, the more expensive it becomes ... I find that’s the biggest struggle for me” – study B

Managing financial constraints is the most connected across all practices. This is about limited or unpredictable incomes, static incomes relative to rising costs, cutting extra expenses, managing being cold, and facing more expensive tariffs (i.e. the poverty premium). This is not about learning to budget; participants deployed many techniques for managing times of the month with no money including considering fruit and vegetables an expendable luxury, filling up with cheaper calories² and choosing long-life foods to reduce waste. Food provision planning becomes harder given multiple uncertainties, including unpredictable incomes. Surplus food was accessed by many and appreciated, but supplies are inconsistent.

² Globally (FAO et al., 2025) and in the UK (Food Foundation, 2025) the most expensive foods per kilocalorie are nutrient dense foods like fruit and vegetables. Eating an unprocessed diet means you would need to eat more food to get the same amount of calories (Brunstrom et al., 2025). Good for losing weight, but not if you need to prioritise feeling full and minimising your food expenditure (Daniel, 2020).

“Fresh is better, but at a certain time of the month, [last week or so] you can’t get the nice fresh food you want. You have to make do with what you’ve got.” – study B

“Eat or put the heating on – you have to choose.” - study E

“My priorities are a roof over my head, then food” – study E

Participants wanted to provide for their families in multiple ways which financial constraints influence, including providing entertainment and pleasure alongside health, stability and choice. This could affect family harmony and parents’ own health.

“I haven’t eaten a lot recently – I just give it to the kids ... I told my kids I ate a late lunch when they asked what I was eating.” – study F

“He says, ‘it’s freezing in here - it’s like walking in a freezer.’ (shrugging) Tough! There’s a blanket in the front room...” – study F

“My kids say, ‘you’re stingy.’” – study F

Although driven by income constraints, some identified practices align with sustainability goals: trying to avoid food waste (often by choosing long-life foods), restricting energy and heating use, and many participants do not have cars. However, in our current societal set-up, these impact quality of life (see 3.1.4).

“Fruit doesn’t keep. It’s handier to keep a packet of biscuits by.” – study H

Cooking knowledge, while useful, faces competition from the need for extra ingredients, requiring fresh food and more forward planning, and costs of buying and using cooking equipment. Where participants cooked, they remained limited in access to fresh food. Participants wanted broader changes so they can have choice and access foods available to higher income people.

“It’s not just the price of the food, the price of cooking has also gone up.” – study F

There was a feeling that decision makers (in industry and politicians) do not understand the realities of people’s lives, what it is like to manage financial constraints every day. For example, the ongoing mental stress and anxiety of trying to make ends meet given the long-term unfolding of austerity, followed by COVID and the cost-of-living crisis. Upset was expressed about industry making big profits and bonuses while others are struggling. Some participants had lost optimism about the future, and distrust of decision makers was expressed. Notably, this included people working and struggling financially.

“People assumed that if you didn’t eat well, it’s because you didn’t have the education or didn’t know how or didn’t want to, but that’s just not true.” – study F

“Come and live for a week in my shoes.” – study F

“it’s never the worker. I can’t get a thing. There’s not a penny out there for me.” – study F

These secondary analysis findings are strengthened by survey results identifying the most significant barriers to eating fruit and veg as price (56%) and wanting to avoid food perishing (61%)³ (n=72, Study K) – both relate to financial constraints.

Contextualising financial constraints

Political influences are strong, including government funding influencing schools and the third sector. Notably, we identified an erosion of trust and disengagement from democratic practices: *“I don’t vote. Why should I bother? They don’t care about us. They don’t do nothing for us” – study F*. This competes against government intervention. Third sector influences include provision of surplus food and other support. This was highly valued by participants when they faced crises, although a system that prevents such crises would be preferable. Such provision is in turn influenced by funding, beliefs that connected and thriving communities lead to good outcomes (motivating engagement), and industry surplus food practices. Other contextual influences include economic turbulence and downturns influenced by global instability (FAO, 2019; Harari, 2024), and increasing wealth inequality in the UK (Bourquin et al., 2024).

3.1.2. Cooking practices: a need for moments of ease

This code encompassed lack of time and needing food that is easy to acquire, prepare and/or consume. Convenience was part of this but conceptually inadequate. An initial interpretation was ‘lack of headspace’, but ‘needing moments of ease’ was a better fit following consultation with locally embedded actors.

The need for moments of ease connects to cooking and shopping practices. It is also connected to managing stress and wellbeing, which are impacted by financial constraints. Working practices further influence, including reducing time and flexibility for food provisioning activities (i.e. shopping, cooking, and eating).

There is competition between participants feeling home-cooked food is healthy and desirable, versus desiring food that is easy to plan, quick to prepare (has everything in it) and requires minimal washing up. Examples include frozen oven-cooked foods and breakfast cereals. This influences kitchen equipment choices, with ovens and air fryers widely used to ‘just chuck something in’. Takeaways and eating out were liked for providing moment of ease and other benefits (see Section 3.2.1).

³ The percentages represent the proportion of people who chose Strongly Agree or Agree for these answers on a 5-point scale from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. There were five options to choose from related to eating fruit and veg and what influenced it.

“I buy frozen jacket potatoes. I don’t care. I buy them because they are quick, easy, 5 minutes in the microwave, done. Dinner is served. I’m not holding my head in shame.”
– study B

“someone else cooks for you. All the kids are happy and don’t complain. You don’t have to wash up.” – study D

Discussions on packaging were contradictory, illustrating varied needs and preferences. The environmental (and health) benefits of reduced plastic packaging were recognised, but many preferred foods in pre-made single portion sizes for ease. Many expressed desires for fruit and vegetables not to be sold in big bags, as often one thing in the bag perishes; yet some described loose fruit and vegetables as less convenient. Notably, participants could not afford waste. Food waste was found to be mainly from food going off or not reusing leftovers (Study A). A few participants talked about freezing leftovers to avoid wastage and for easy future meals. However, freezer-to-oven foods are not suited to this, and preparing large amounts of food to freeze requires time, energy and budget.

Contextualising a need for moments of ease

These dynamics are influenced by changing lifestyles and working practices, entangled with industry and technological development (Jabs and Devine, 2006; Jackson and Viehoff, 2016). Indeed, participants described having to provide food quickly (e.g. quick convenient lunches) which was supported by easy to prepare food. Government employment regulations also influence working practices and, thus, time available for food provisioning. Economic dynamics alongside government and market decisions additionally contribute to people’s financial constraints and resultant stress (Wickham et al., 2020; Baxter et al., 2025). One stress management strategy is making things easier where you can, such as seeking moments of ease in food provisioning.

3.1.3. Eating practices: Taste, texture and visual appeal - ‘selective’ children

Selective children exert a strong influence on food choices in some households. The reasons identified for ‘selective eaters’ varied from intolerances to neurodiversity, with parents of neurodiverse children often citing sensory issues, habits and difficulties in building familiarity. All have material impacts on busy parents trying to ensure children *are* fed (in the face of refusal) and to maintain family harmony to ease their own stress and wellbeing.

“I say no ... then with autism and ADHD we get the biggest meltdown. Swearing, throwing things, smacking...” – study D

“As long as they have eaten, it doesn’t matter what it is.” – study D

Participants cared about providing health and energy for their families. They viewed fruits, vegetables and home-cooked foods as desirable and healthy. Many discussed hiding vegetables in food, although that requires cooking knowledge, time and energy. Some 'bargained' with healthy food consumption in exchange for treats, for others this did not work. Many worried about children's diets. However, parents also wanted to provide family wellbeing through enjoyment, happiness, comfort and choice (which financial constraints influence). Some described not wanting to reproduce their parents' practices: *"when we were younger our parents said eat it or starve, so we are less picky. I don't do that to my kids."* – study B

Children's widespread snacking on crisps and sweet treats was extensively discussed. Some children also snacked on fruits, but unfortunately, most children preferred expensive fruits (e.g. berries) and inconsistency in eating fruits led to unaffordable waste.

Many participants expressed general reluctance to experiment with new foods as they could not afford waste if food was not eaten, including some children only accepting certain brands. Conversely, some enjoyed experimenting with new dishes. These practices directly compete; financial constraints are one mediating factor.

Participants (especially mothers) cooked different meals for household members with different preferences or food intolerances (including adults). A few adult participants described not enjoying many types of fruit and vegetables themselves. Some said their own diet suffered from following children's food requirements. Participants noted the importance of texture and visual appeal alongside taste; and expressed concerns about marketing and advertising influencing children. They suggested fruit and vegetables have potential to be visually appealing.

Parents described selective children sometimes refusing to eat school meals, and difficulties affording packed lunches. Increased dialogue and collaborative action with schools was the 2nd highest priority for action in one ranking exercise (n=72, Study K). The cost of free-from food was also challenging.

"Whether an item is more or less expensive, you just have to work around the food intolerances. I've got credit cards and getting myself in more debt, but that's what it is being a mum and I wouldn't give it up for the world." – study B

Contextualising children's eating practices

Children's eating practices in our findings (and in most communities) are influenced strongly by politics (e.g. education funding, curriculum decisions, family support), the third sector (e.g. provision of fun food-related activities) and socio-cultural influences (e.g. family backgrounds and children's expectations around food). These are linked to development of an unhealthy food environment including market influences and advertising (Story et al.,

2008), peer modelling (Salvy et al., 2012), and, potentially, the proximity of healthy or unhealthy food outlets to schools (Barrett et al., 2017; Caruso et al., 2024).

3.1.4. Shopping practices: Physical accessibility

Accessibility was a salient concept with the word or related concepts appearing in multiple shopping-related codes. However, it was used in different ways (e.g. related to physical proximity or affordability) and affected people differently. Shopping particularly felt like a burden for those managing small children (especially without a car), those with physical or mental health conditions, those managing financial constraints, and those with several of these challenges.

Not being able to get to the shops was the third biggest barrier to eating fruit and veg (40%, n=72, Study K) and particularly affected those without a car. Shopping experiences varied; 29% disliked shopping, 30% were indifferent and 41% liked it (n=72, Study K). Having less money and/or small children were correlated⁴ with less enjoyable shopping experiences (Study K). Participants shopped frequently (25% shop daily, n=60, Study A), compared to UK averages (15% of women, 19% of men - Statista, 2020). Men shopped more frequently than women (Study A). Frequency did not only depend on car access, but car access influenced *where* people could shop.

Many described why shopping required extra time, including difficulties forward-planning meals to enable bigger shops (due to various sources of uncertainty and stress), not having resources to bulk-buy, not being able to carry shopping home (due to not having a car) *“I need to buy more than I can carry.” – study K*, and using multiple shops to obtain the products or prices required. Notably, some depended on one shop because, *“it is the only supermarket I can get to” – study A*. Working and parenting practices influenced time available: *“I’m retired so it’s easy to get to the shops” – study A*.

Improved accessibility included shops having a variety of affordable products, including world foods, and well-stocked shelves so participants could get what they needed in one trip. Supermarkets often met these criteria and were used by most participants (79%, n=72, Study K)⁵. Online shopping was disliked due to substitutions, wanting to personally select items, and the need to do a big shop to avoid delivery fees, which results in a high single spend and extra forward planning. Notably, many people selected meals while shopping according to special offers on the day.

Contextualising physical access challenges

These accessibility challenges are influenced by market and corporate decisions (e.g. locations of food retail or takeaway outlets and which foods are stocked) and urban planning

⁴ This was a linear regression which was statistically significant at 95% confidence interval

⁵ 79% (n=60) got most of their food from supermarkets, and about 20% got most of their food from small food stores (Study A). Only 10% did not use small food stores at all (Study A).

policies (Chang et al., 2022). The findings illustrate how these infrastructural influences intersect with socio-economic phenomena such as policy decisions resulting in financial constraints (Power et al., 2021) and complex intersections with ill-health and low incomes (Ridley et al., 2020). Participants also described third-sector offerings as an important route for accessing food, services and support.

3.2. Competing practices

The food practice with the most ‘competitive’ connections was managing wellbeing (Table 4). Many highly competing practices relate to money or health management (similarly to the nexus practices).

Table 4: Practices with the most competitive relationships.

Parent code	Practice	Practice type	Connections*
Health management practices	Managing wellbeing	Competency (skill)	7
Eating practices	Allergies or dietary restrictions	Material (thing)	6
Eating practices	Food as a source of health	Meaning (motivation)	6
Shopping practices	Cost of food	Material (thing)	6
Money management practices	Managing financial constraints	Competency (skill)	6

*All other identified practices had fewer than five connections.

3.2.1. Health management practices: managing wellbeing

Participants cared about their and their children's health and valued fruit, vegetables and home-cooked food. They expressed concerns about chemicals and additives in food. Health was a higher priority than environmental considerations. In one survey, 72% stated there were things about their diet they would like to change, and of the changes requested 80% were to do with making diets healthier (n=72, Study K). Wanting to eat more fruits and vegetables was also a top priority during community feedback (Study J). Healthy eating practices faced substantial competition including food costs, and many prioritised taste and texture to provide foods the family would accept and eat.

Managing health is broader than healthy eating, encompassing managing stress, wellbeing and energy. There are complex interactions with managing financial constraints, including competition from finance-related stress, anxiety and family friction; experiencing cold (not affording heating); and exhaustion from working longer hours. Managing wellbeing includes entertainment, treats, social connection, maintaining family harmony, and rests from domestic chores. Takeaways and eating out were liked for providing these benefits, despite their expense. This is highly connected to the need for moments of ease - saving time, energy, stress and headspace.

“I want my kids to have a chippie tea on a Friday night.” – study B

“There is a psychological connection ... I’m having a treat and I deserve it.” – study B

“Don’t have to do any washing up.” – study B

Wellbeing was also affected by the mental toll of various types of stigma: around not affording things, around seeking support, and being patronised that you do not understand healthy eating or that it is just about motivation. Participants suggested labelling foods as 'good' and 'bad' can be unhelpful and adds to the burden people are managing.

“You feel like you’ve failed, or you can’t meet your own needs.” – study F

“5-a-day makes you feel really incompetent.” – study B

Contextualising managing wellbeing

Food labelling and ingredients in processed foods (which participants cared about) are subject to multiple influences, including market dynamics and corporate decisions, food safety practices and government regulation. It is notable that managing wellbeing often competed with other practices, with strong socio-cultural influences including public narratives such as guilt or pressure to be a certain weight, and stigma around receiving food or other support (Loopstra, 2018; Hunt et al., 2023). As described previously, wellbeing is also affected by the pressures of having a low income (Ridley et al., 2020). Participants again highlighted the third sector as offering face-to-face support and social connection; in one ranking exercise more support for community venues came out as the top priority for action (n=72, Study K).

4. Discussion

FoodSEqual’s data were gathered over 5-years, including multiple iterations of community input. Whitley residents made proposals for change throughout. This discussion section is based on these proposals (see the detailed list of participants’ proposals in supplementary materials).

4.1. Broadly connected financial constraints, acting upstream and sideways

“financial constraints strongly influence the ability to choose and consume healthier foods and drinks” (DEFRA, 2024, sect.4.3.2).

Previous studies (including FoodSEqual) suggest affordability is the biggest barrier to healthy food access for low-income populations (Puddephatt et al., 2020; Power et al., 2021; Wagstaff et al., 2025). Our results extend this, aligning with others to further illuminate multiple ways financial constraints influence food practices, connecting across multiple bundles of practices, including management of health, wellbeing and stress; parenting and leisure; mobility and shopping; and cooking and food waste management. For example,

cutting expenditures on entertainment activities increases the importance of takeaways or unhealthy snack foods as a family treat and cohesion activity (Isaacs et al., 2022; Hunt et al., 2023; van Kesteren and Evans, 2025). Not affording waste reduces experimentation with new foods and purchases of perishable foods (Daniel, 2020; Puddephatt et al., 2020; Hunt et al., 2023; van Kesteren and Evans, 2025). Perceptions of fruits and vegetables as expendable luxuries influence choices (Ravikumar et al., 2022). Our results further highlight the compounding nature of inequalities, such as barriers to bulk-buying and bulk cooking meaning more is spent on food.

Participants' proposals included targeted cash incentives for food, and there is a good case for this (Loopstra, 2018). The costs of providing everyone in the UK a diet meeting Eatwell plate⁶ guidelines is estimated at £57 billion, which is £210 billion less than estimated health-related costs of current diets (Jackson, 2024). But given the broad connections of financial constraints across multiple food-related practices, we join others to argue for addressing their root causes and the related structural factors (Griffin et al., 2021; Power et al., 2021; Ravikumar et al., 2022).

Indeed, our participants' proposals included 'upstream'⁷ preventative interventions (similarly to Stone et al., 2024; Hunter et al., 2025), alongside proposals that could be described as 'sideways' interventions; representing lateral thinking beyond food. For example, participants proposed alleviating financial constraints by improving working conditions, wages and routes to work (see also Power et al., 2021). Influences from working practices are evident across our findings and those of previous studies (Devine et al., 2006; Pfeiffer et al., 2017). Our participants also proposed free bus passes and leisure activities for children, aligning with previous proposals for investment in local social infrastructure (e.g. parks and activity centres) (Isaacs et al., 2022). Free travel for children is already in place in London (TFL, 2026), but without central government funding, it is unlikely that many places will be able to enact such measures. The UK government recently announced a suite of measures to reduce financial hardship (DWP, 2026). But it does not extend to what is proposed here, and whether implementation will be effective remains to be seen.

Furthermore, existing conceptions of social and health equities can lead to narrow interpretations of concepts such as 'upstream interventions' (McMahon, 2022), rather than a systemic view of prevention. Most interventions do not fit neatly into the binary of

⁶ The Eatwell Plate is highly critiqued, including for inappropriate food industry influence on its design, its distance from current diets, and lack of environmental sustainability considerations (Rayner, 2025). Others highlight the Eatwell Plate is culturally inappropriate and 'othering' for some UK residents and propose alternatives (Manchester Food Board, n.d.). More radical perspectives critique its disconnection from food system injustices, the impact of inequalities on health, and its role in perpetuating harmful and individual-responsibility focused narratives (Aphramor, 2024).

⁷ The upstream metaphor aims to draw attention to addressing the underlying causes of a health inequalities, rather than the symptoms (Campbell et al., 2025). This includes examining structural policies that impact across lives and social norms (Campbell et al., 2025), and thinking about preventative interventions to 'stop people falling in the river' (Lundberg, 2020).

upstream-downstream (Campbell et al., 2025). To be effective, interventions must also attend to the intersectional nature of inequalities and the underlying social processes that shape social determinants (Hankivsky and Christoffersen, 2008). Additionally, our findings identified concerns that government actions would only support people on benefits (not those in work and struggling) or might reduce other benefit entitlements. Many participants expressed distrust in government decision makers, as these are often people with money and very different lived/living experiences. Effective implementation of policies or interventions is partly co-created with the public who can engage, ignore or resist them (Ostrom, 1978; Pestoff et al., 2012). Thus, there is a need to build mutual understanding and trust to work collectively towards change.

4.1.1. Market and community interventions for food waste

Reducing food waste is part of sustainability and food security goals (UN, 2022). Food waste interacted with participants' food practices in several ways. Firstly, as surplus food being redistributed through community initiatives. However, supplies were unreliable and often close to perishing (Foodrise, 2025), contributing to difficulties planning food provisioning. Participants' proposals included better coordination around use-by dates and processing perishing food into ready meals. Research suggests the food industry could be willing to do this if given incentives, alongside highlighting many ways this 'hybrid food chain' could be improved (Sawyer et al., 2023). More attention is required in this area.

Second, our findings align with others who conclude that not affording waste affects food selection during cooking and shopping (Daniel, 2020; Hunt et al., 2023). Participant proposals to address this include making perishable items available in equally affordable but smaller or flexible portion sizes; for some foods, pre-made single portions were preferred for ease. Here interventions with supermarkets and higher up the supply chain may be appropriate (Bridle et al., 2025), especially given the influence of growth-focused food producers shaping 'on the go' food provisioning (Hirth et al., 2021). Nonetheless, multiple smaller packages likely mean increased manufacturing costs and packaging waste compared with singular items containing multiple servings. Feasibility and trade-offs need exploration.

Community tasting sessions to de-risk experimentation with new foods were also a popular proposal, aligning with previous literature (Daniel, 2020). Participants further proposed peer-to-peer skill sharing around use and preservation of leftover foods. Although some studies suggest that increasing meal planning knowledge and skills can be impactful (Romani et al., 2018), it is important to remember the barriers presented across our findings. These include access to kitchen equipment and time or energy for food-related activities such as preparation and meal planning. The latter is further hindered by unpredictable incomes and lives. To enable food practices around bulk-buying, bulk cooking and use of leftovers these barriers must be overcome.

4.2. Targeting interventions for accessibility across the life course and in place

Beyond food retailer location there were multiple reasons why extra time was needed for shopping (as outlined in 3.1.4). Similar to previous studies, these are often related to financial constraints (Power et al., 2021). Physical accessibility is highly related to health and life circumstances (Puddephatt et al., 2020), so was a particular challenge for certain people (see Section 3.1.4), and our participants proposed targeted interventions. Given the influence of life circumstances (e.g. caring responsibilities), targeted intervention design could consider how constraints and opportunities shift over everyone's lives (the life course perspective⁸) (Lundberg, 2020). Life-course events, such as becoming a parent, are useful targets for new food practice adoption (Plessz et al., 2016), as they are key to establishing food choice trajectories (Sobal and Bisogni, 2009).

Another important accessibility-related concept is 'food deserts' which relates to proximity, affordability and availability of healthy food options (Smith and Thompson, 2022). Although the Whitley area referred to in the case study had reasonable proximity to food retail outlets, the persistence of heterogeneous place-based health inequalities (Marmot et al., 2020) indicates the importance of considering place when designing physical access interventions (Smith and Thompson, 2022).

4.3. Broader approaches to managing health and wellbeing

Participants' proposals for health-related actions focused on the affordability of healthy food and addressing unhealthy additives and chemicals. However, similar to Isaacs et al. (2022), we found participants used food environments to meet broader wellbeing needs, sometimes at the expense of nutritional needs. People *understand* and *care* about healthy eating but manage wider life circumstances and constraints (Rylatt and Cartwright, 2016; Power et al., 2021; Ravikumar et al., 2022; Hunt et al., 2023; van Kesteren and Evans, 2025). Furthermore, there are complex relationships between financial insecurity, food insecurity, increased psychological distress and food-choice motivations (Evans et al., 2025). Struggling to afford food has a mental and emotional toll (Hunter et al., 2025) and can increase stress and worsen mental or physical health (Puddephatt et al., 2020). Long-term financial hardship can also influence mental and physical health (Mallorie, 2024), as can experiencing discrimination or stigma (poverty-related or otherwise) (Davis, 2020; Inglis et al., 2023). In turn, worsened health can worsen economic outcomes (Ridley et al., 2020), potentially creating vicious cycles.

⁸ Designing targeted interventions from this perspective would mean differentiating between factors affecting all members of particular social groups and those driving variation within groups to identify universal challenges occurring over life courses alongside awareness of how results are affected by inequalities (Lundberg, 2020)

We join others to argue that policies and interventions need to work with broader definitions of managing health and wellbeing (McCartney et al., 2019), which incorporate healthy eating alongside managing stress, energy, social relations and emotional, mental and physical health (Hawkes et al., 2024). Precedent for this at the local level of UK governance includes Joint Strategic Needs Assessments⁹ (Tomlinson et al., 2013). These need expansion and national government investment to support the aims outlined here. Our participants wanted more government support for community hubs that provide face-to-face support and social connection (a top priority in one ranking exercise, n=72, Study K). Such spaces can help people address multiple challenges interconnected with diet inequalities. Unfortunately, both long-standing institutional practices, and the narrow conceptions of health underlying them, can constrain attempts to address wider determinants (McMahon, 2023). These need to be overcome for broader approaches to be delivered.

4.4. Moments of ease across the food environment, lifestyles and society

Previous research similarly found that low-wage parents deploy food-choice strategies to reduce time and effort in food preparation, and manage stress and fatigue (Devine et al., 2006; Rylatt and Cartwright, 2016; Ravikumar et al., 2022). However, no income group in the UK fully meets diet recommendations (DEFRA, 2024). Multiple society-wide changes have influenced time scarcity related to food provisioning (Jabs and Devine, 2006), for example, current working practices encourage quick convenient lunches (Pfeiffer et al., 2017). This impacts food practices across income brackets (Carrigan et al., 2006; Bava et al., 2008; Vos et al., 2022; Laila et al., 2023). Interpretations of ‘home-cooked food’ have also evolved, including acceptance of some convenience ingredients to reduce (often gendered) labour (Moisio et al., 2004; Carrigan et al., 2006). These changing practices are intertwined with changing lifestyles, social expectations (including more women entering the workforce)¹⁰ and technical innovation (Jackson and Viehoff, 2016). Whilst it is essential to identify and address inequalities, it is also important not to perpetuate stereotypes by suggesting that phenomena such as convenience foods are mainly present in low-income communities.

The UK is stuck in a ‘junk food cycle’¹¹ with regulatory responses required (Dimbleby, 2021). UK regulatory responses are critiqued for focusing on individual behaviour change rather than addressing wider determinants of health (Griffin et al., 2021) or affordability and the

⁹ See official guidance from the Department of Health (2022)

¹⁰ Some suggest convenience foods were part of technologies that enabled women to enter the workforce and take on additional labour without reducing their domestic labour, by enabling domestic work to be completed more efficiently – see O’Connell et al. (2015).

¹¹ This is where the profitability of unhealthy foods leads to more investment in their development and advertising, leading to more consumption, an even bigger market and the Junk Food Cycle continues (Dimbleby, 2021)

food environment (Doherty et al., 2022; Briazu et al., 2024)¹². One income-related difference is inequalities of choice, and higher-priced convenience food is *sometimes* healthier, which FoodSEqual aimed to address by co-creating more affordable, healthy convenience products. Policies supporting healthier products to be more affordable could be useful (Hunter et al., 2025), although FoodSEqual uncovered market barriers related to financial feasibility and consumer demand. Additionally, implementation of such policies should consider participant suspicion of the origins, ingredients and safety of processed foods (Moisio et al., 2004; Carrigan et al., 2006), and the emerging evidence base around possible health impacts from certain additives and preservatives (e.g. Hasenböhler et al., 2026; Pinto et al., 2026). More research, regulations and public engagement are needed to support trust and acceptability.

Practice theory further argues that convenience foods are popular because they ‘fit in’ with the routines and rhythms of food-related and other practices across people’s lives (Jackson and Viehoff, 2016). Although this illuminates the need to address societal expectations developed in tandem with use of convenience foods, the structural inequalities constraining people’s actions must not be forgotten. Wealth and place-based inequalities affect the foods accessed (Smith and Thompson, 2022), and low incomes create further inequalities of ease that affect consumption of healthy food (van Kesteren and Evans, 2025). For example, lacking access to appropriate cooking equipment (van Kesteren and Evans, 2025), or not being able to ‘buy in’ time saving measures such as paying a cleaner (Cohen, 1998). Related to broader wellbeing, we thus offer the novel concept of ‘a need for moments of ease’. It specifies and moves away from ‘convenience’ which is a broad, complex and ‘moralised’ category (Jackson and Viehoff, 2016). This may support the design of novel interventions to influence everyday food practices. For example, affordable public diners could offer such moments of ease (Kinniburgh, 2025), although support in non-food aspects of life could also be considered. Notably, our research was mainly with White British people. Inequalities of ease might unfold differently for those from other cultural backgrounds, and mapping inequalities of ease would be a useful area for further research.

4.5. Engaging children, the whole family and community in diet change

Food provisioning is strongly influenced by taste, habits and familiarity among family members, particularly children. Our finding that children’s preferences influence household diets affirms many others (Puddephatt et al., 2020; Ravikumar et al., 2022; Vos et al., 2022; Laila et al., 2023). Children refusing food has been a challenge since the 19th century (Landau-Czajka, 2002), and likely before. Nonetheless, others similarly document relaxation

¹² In 2025, a policy paper outlining priorities for the food system appeared to indicate a shift in direction, with discussion of the junk food cycle, affordability, and the food environment (DEFRA, 2025a). It remains to be seen how implementation will unfold, with activists highlighting over representation of food industry actors in engagement processes (Tarman, 2025).

of parental food control across generations (MacDonald et al., 2018), and describe food as bundled with broader family practices including emotional management and provision of love (Rylatt and Cartwright, 2016; MacDonald et al., 2018). Highly influential contextual changes include the nutrition transition; a societal-wide shift towards diets high in refined carbohydrates, saturated fats, sodium and sugar – increasingly consumed as pre-processed foods (Popkin and Ng, 2022). Eating behaviours have been impacted by these ‘obesogenic food environments’ which feature high availability and promotion of unhealthy foods (Osei-Assibey et al., 2012).

The interlocking practices identified in our findings affirm that simply implementing cooking classes or knowledge campaigns is unlikely to be effective (Power et al., 2021; Hodder et al., 2024). For example, not affording food waste can drive parental risk aversion to introducing new foods, leading children to be familiar with and accept only a narrow range of foods. Repeat exposure is the most effective method for increasing food liking and consumption among children (Holley et al., 2017; Mohd Nor et al., 2021), and can include non-taste sensory engagements (e.g. visual, touch, smell) (Dazeley and Houston-Price, 2015), with 7-14 exposures needed to build acceptance (Holley et al., 2017). Participant proposals for change align with this, emphasising activities to support children’s familiarity with healthy foods. Participants were particularly keen on dialogue and collaboration between parents and schools (the 2nd highest priority for action in one ranking exercise, n=72, study K). Delivery of this would require resourcing and sensitivity, as some parents may have had negative experiences with schools (Lloyd-Evans and the Whitley Researchers, 2021). De-risking new food experimentation through community tasting sessions was another popular proposal. During FoodSEqual, we worked with community partners to offer ‘fun with food days’ that provided opportunities for children to touch, draw, play and taste new foods. These events had positive feedback and good results in terms of children trying new foods. Obtaining funding for such activities can be challenging.

Furthermore, our findings affirmed that family food practices are intertwined with many bundles of practices, including work, school, and family activities (MacDonald et al., 2018; Wright-Pedersen et al., 2026); aligning with participant proposals that interventions could include the whole family or even community. Shifting practices requires shifts in lifestyles and surrounding environments. This includes modelling by parents or peers as useful complementary measures within interventions, although parental modelling alone is less impactful (Holley et al., 2017). All this strengthens the case for place-based approaches¹³ co-designed with participants to identify key influences across their lives (McGowan et al., 2021; Bridle et al., 2025). Such interventions must take care not to create or exacerbate stigma, nor to just benefit people in the community who already have higher levels of

¹³ Place-based approaches focus on collaborative action in a specific location, aiming to reduce geographic inequalities (Campbell et al., 2025).

resources (Campbell et al., 2025; McCartney and Popay, 2025), and should include children's perspectives at the design stage (Wright-Pedersen et al., 2026).

The influence of advertising on children and young people was also noted by our participants, and is highly discussed (e.g. Story et al., 2008; Dimbleby, 2021; Ravikumar et al., 2022). A junk food advertising ban was recently announced in the UK (DHSC, 2026), although commentators highlight that loopholes mean that children can still be reached (Health Foundation, 2026). Finally, there is an emerging evidence base on the impact of the food environment and advertising on adolescents (Tsochantaridou et al., 2023), and the potential for this transition age as a key intervention point (Neufeld et al., 2022).

4.6. Addressing normative inequality and increasing public participation

Normative judgements about what is appropriate (e.g. appropriate cooking practices) relate to social hierarchy and experiences of social inequality, particularly 'normative inequality' where some practices are judged to be morally superior (Halkier and Holm, 2021). In our practice analysis examples of 'normative inequality' included people feeling judged for not 'eating 5 a day' whilst their circumstances constrain them. This aligns with previous findings that being priced out of healthy food reinforced feelings of stigma about having a low income (Power et al., 2021). We also identified stigma associated with accessing food support, which is well known (Loopstra, 2018; Hunt et al., 2023). Informal food aid may provide a more positive experience, such as community projects where food is freely available for anyone (Power et al., 2021), aligning with our participants' proposals for 'barrier-free' food support.

Stigma is one mechanism through which economic injustice and wealth inequality are justified, and therefore perpetuated (Sutton et al., 2014; Tyler and Campbell, 2024). Stigma has multiple impacts, including on aspirations, community identities and relationships (Lloyd-Evans and the Whitley Researchers, 2021). Furthermore, negative stereotypes and public narratives around people with low incomes can influence policymaking and public interventions (Cairney, 2019; van Kesteren and Evans, 2025) and public opinions about intervention (Reutter et al., 2002; Orford, 2025).

The idea that decision makers do not understand the realities of people's lives came up multiple times, with distrust and the need for more understanding expressed. One approach to increasing trust is to *meaningfully involve people in decisions* about services that affect them (see Gibbs and Mutebi, 2026). Relatedly, there is a need to avoid using language that is patronising, disrespectful or frames groups negatively, and to challenge underlying assumptions and narratives (Lloyd-Evans and the Whitley Researchers, 2021; Fielding-Singh and Oleschuk, 2023; Aphramor, 2024). Use of stigmatising language creates an additional emotional burden for people with lived/living experience who engage in participatory

processes (Lloyd-Evans and the Whitley Researchers, 2021). Language used should be co-designed with participants and collaborators (NIHR, 2021).

5. Limitations

Halkier and Holm (2021) suggest that social practice research should create detailed mappings of household members' daily routines to understand how these relate to food practices. Our secondary data analysis could not capture such an in-depth picture, but rather offers value in the breadth of data. Another limitation and potential source of bias is the focus of the primary research, and that the majority of participants were white British, lived in one specific area and were women. The research team was also comprised mostly of women.

The NVivo analysis included only one coder. Bias from this was mitigated through iterative consultation throughout the design, analysis and writing up with locally embedded actors and co-authors who gathered the original data; reflexive participant collaboration (Motulsky, 2021). This shaped the research design and questions, code names, theme selection, discussion and conclusions.

6. Conclusions

We join others to argue transforming food inequalities will require transdisciplinary efforts, coordinating diverse and multi-level approaches (Isaacs et al., 2022; Bridle et al., 2025; Wagstaff et al., 2025), and that this must reach beyond food (Passidomo, 2013; Wright-Pedersen et al., 2026). We propose prioritising addressing the root causes of financial constraints and situating healthy eating among broader wellbeing needs, which include a need for moments of ease. A cross-government Ministerial Food Strategy Group and Food Advisory Group recently formed in the UK (DEFRA, 2025b) could support actioning these aims, and the 'twelve realities' framework by Hawkes et al., (2024) could guide efforts to consider people's broader lives. A key contribution of our article is reframing the desire for convenience foods into 'a need for moments of ease'. Further research is needed to test and explore the utility of this concept, and the relationship between broader wellbeing needs and diet. We also emphasise that increased consumption of convenience foods is part of broad societal shifts and not isolated in low-income communities, although accessibility and affordability of healthy foods do need action.

Furthermore, our contribution affirms that shifting focus from health behaviours to health practices can illuminate leverage points for food environment interventions (Mattioni et al., 2020). Transcending dichotomised thinking of 'structural inequalities and context' versus 'individual agency' (Wright-Pedersen et al., 2026), the food practice lens enabled identification and targeting of diverse intervention approaches (consolidated recommendations in table 5). Different approaches have differing benefits and limitations,

so appraisal of assumptions, change mechanisms and potential unintended consequences is needed (Campbell et al., 2025). Systems approaches have the potential to integrate multiple intervention approaches across individual and structural levels (Campbell et al., 2025), and FoodSEqual and others in the wider funded consortium were guided by systems approaches (Horton et al., 2025). We suggest that future interventions must attend to decisions about where to draw the boundaries of systems as this influences the approaches taken, and that integration of equity perspectives needs attention (Campbell et al., 2025). Interventions must also respond to contextual and challenge-specific nuances, and involving communities as co-designers can facilitate this (Pettinger et al., 2023; Zorbas et al., 2023; Bridle et al., 2025; Wagstaff et al., 2025) – if delivered well (see recommendations: Lloyd-Evans and Oenga, 2023; Wagstaff et al., 2025; Gardiner et al., 2026b).

Another key thread throughout our findings is the experiences and impacts of stigma. This impacts wellbeing and adds to the burden people carry from ongoing experiences of economic injustice. To facilitate the kind of cross-societal collaboration described above, it is necessary to address harmful stereotypes and bias about people with low incomes and their lives (Lloyd-Evans and the Whitley Researchers, 2021; Tyler and Campbell, 2024) (see Section 4.6). We further identified a loss of optimism and lack of trust in government intervention. We highlight participatory approaches as a way to increase trust and engagement (Gibbs and Mutebi, 2026) and to support the development of hope and collective action (Gardiner et al., 2026a). Collaboration can enable the development of understanding, articulation of aspirations, and co-creation of contextually appropriate solutions. At a local level this means things being done ‘by’ and not ‘to’ or ‘for’ communities (Russell, 2019; Russell and McKnight, 2022); supporting people to make change collectively in ways which are not stigmatizing.

Table 5: Consolidated findings and recommendations (full list of participant’s proposals in the supplementary materials).

Finding	Recommendations
Managing financial constraints was the most connected practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upstream and ‘sideways’ interventions, including improving conditions for workers and routes to work and regulating the property market. This should be alongside targeted cash or voucher interventions. • Market-based interventions to improve (1) distribution of surplus food, and (2) making perishable food available in affordable small portion sizes to prevent food waste (which people can’t afford). • Community interventions around bulk cooking and use of leftovers. Alongside increasing knowledge and skills, this should address practical barriers to uptake of these food practices.
A ‘need for moments of ease’ was the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interventions can identify how to offer moments of ease, either in terms of food provisioning or across people’s

second most connected practice	<p>lives. This is proposed as an alternative to ‘convenience’ and is part of broader wellbeing needs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies to make healthier convenience products more affordable (reducing inequalities of choice). Alongside research, regulation and public engagement to support trust in the safety of such products.
The influence of selective children was the fourth most connected practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family and community activities to support child familiarity of foods, and de-risk experimentation with new foods (e.g. community cooking and tasting sessions). This includes increased dialogue and collaboration between parents and schools. • Place-based approaches co-designed in context to identify key influences across people’s lives and the multiple settings they interact in (e.g. school, work, leisure, home). • Regulatory responses to address advertising influences (some are underway).
Accessibility was particularly highlighted in community feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted interventions which consider changing circumstances across the life course alongside socio-economic and place-based inequities.
Managing wellbeing was the practice with the most competitive relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and interventions to treat healthy eating as part of broader wellbeing needs (e.g. managing stress, energy, social and community group relations, enjoyment and moments of ease).
Experiences of stigma were evident across findings, impacting wellbeing and participation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research, policy and interventions must attend to income-related stigma alongside other forms of discrimination. This includes improving lines of communication, considering language used and disrupting underlying assumptions and narratives (see Tyler and Campbell, 2024; Robertson et al., 2025).

Acknowledgements

Thank you to all the community researchers who supported and shaped this research, and to the community partners and other community actors who engaged in providing iterative feedback throughout the analysis and write-up. We also acknowledge the work of all the community partners and academic researchers who delivered the primary data collection over the five years of FoodSEqual, upon which this secondary analysis was based.

Data statement

The data from the study will be stored in an online repository, and a DOI will be made available here prior to publication. Data access is possible upon request.

Ethical approval statement

The secondary analysis use of the data is in line with the ethical approval and participant consent sheets in the primary research. The primary studies were approved by the University of Reading Research Ethics Committee at the University of Reading, references: SREC 2021/22; SREC 21/2022; SREC 2-21/22; SREC 38/2022 (with additional amendments).

Funding statement

This research is funded by the project entitled Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities (FoodSEqual, BB/V004905/1), one of four consortia projects focused on food systems transformation, funded by the UKRI Strategic Priorities Fund 2021 – 2025. The funding body had no role in the study design, analysis or data interpretation.

Declaration of conflicting interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Author contributions

Bramble Gardiner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2246-8320>

Conceptualization (lead), Data Curation (lead), Formal analysis (lead), Investigation (lead), Methodology (lead), Project administration (supporting), Validation (equal), Visualization (lead), Writing – original draft (lead), Writing – review & editing (lead),

Lorna Zischka <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7895-9268>

Conceptualization (lead), Data Curation (lead), Formal analysis (supporting), Investigation (lead), Methodology (supporting), Project administration (supporting), Validation (equal), Visualization (supporting), Writing – original draft (lead), Writing – review & editing (lead)

Sally Lloyd-Evans <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4234-4269>

Conceptualization (lead), Data Curation (supporting), Formal analysis (supporting), Investigation (supporting), Methodology (lead), Project administration (lead), Resources (lead), Supervision (lead), Validation (equal), Visualization (supporting), Writing – original draft (supporting), Writing – review & editing (supporting)

Lisa Methven <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6940-7579>

Data Curation (supporting), Investigation (supporting), Validation (equal), Visualization (supporting), Writing – original draft (supporting), Writing – review & editing (supporting)

Carol Wagstaff <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9400-8641>

Conceptualization (supporting), Investigation (supporting), Methodology (supporting), Project administration (lead), Resources (lead), Supervision (supporting), Validation (equal), Visualization (supporting), Writing – original draft (supporting), Writing – review & editing (supporting)

References

Aphramor, L., (2024) Reframing nutrition beyond the healthy/unhealthy binary | Food Ethics Council. *Food Ethics Council | Fair and resilient food systems*. Available at: <https://www.foodethicscouncil.org/opinion/reframing-nutrition-beyond-the-binary/> [Accessed 8 Jan. 2026].

Araújo, S.H. de, Hamid, S.C. and do Rego, A.G., (2022) Urban food environments and cultural adequacy: the (dis)assemblage of urban halal food environments in Muslim minority contexts. *Food, Culture & Society*. [online] Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15528014.2021.1933773> [Accessed 10 Mar. 2026].

Barrett, M., Crozier, S., Lewis, D., Godfrey, K., Robinson, S., Cooper, C., Inskip, H., Baird, J. and Vogel, C., (2017) Greater access to healthy food outlets in the home and school environment is associated with better dietary quality in young children. *Public Health Nutrition*, 2018, pp.3316–3325.

Bava, C.M., Jaeger, S.R. and Park, J., (2008) Constraints upon food provisioning practices in ‘busy’ women’s lives: Trade-offs which demand convenience. *Appetite*, 502, pp.486–498.

Baxter, A., Tindall, M., Wickham, S., Marimpi, M., Brown, H.W., Monford, L., Sutton, M., Richiardi, M., Cheetam, M., Amo-Agyei, S., Taylor-Robinson, D., Bambra, C., Katikireddi, S.V. and Craig, P., (2025) *A difference-in-differences analysis of the well-being effects of Universal*

Credit. [Working Paper] CeMPA Working Paper Series. Available at: <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/324387> [Accessed 13 Oct. 2025].

Bourquin, P., Brewer, M. and Wernham, T., (2024) Trends in income and wealth inequalities. *Oxford Open Economics*, 3Supplement_1, pp.i103–i146.

Briazu, R.A., Masood, F., Hunt, L., Pettinger, C., Wagstaff, C. and McCloy, R., (2024) Barriers and facilitators to healthy eating in disadvantaged adults living in the UK: a scoping review. *BMC Public Health*, 241, p.1770.

Bridle, S., Parsons, K., Poppy, G., Duncombe, T., Dicks, L.V., Doherty, B., Johnstone, A., Reynolds, C., Wagstaff, C., Lyon, F., Buckton, S., Dare, B., White, M., Yap, C., Shahrokni, R., Bhunnoo, R., Mitchell, H., Fazey, I., Moran, D., Turner, C., Beacham, J., Ingram, J., Jackson, P., Wells, R., Denby, K., Macmillan, T., Brunstrom, J.M. and Bryant, M., (2025) Key action areas for transforming the UK food system: insights from the Transforming UK Food Systems (TUKFS) Programme project portfolio. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 3801935, p.20240166.

Browne, J.L., Ventura, A., Mosely, K. and Speight, J., (2013) 'I call it the blame and shame disease': a qualitative study about perceptions of social stigma surrounding type 2 diabetes. *BMJ Open*, 311, p.e003384.

Brunstrom, J.M., Schatzker, M., Rogers, P.J., Courville, A.B., Hall, K.D. and Flynn, A.N., (2025) Consuming an unprocessed diet reduces energy intake: a post-hoc analysis of a randomized controlled trial reveals a role for human nutritional intelligence. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, p.101183.

Cairney, P., (2019) The UK government's imaginative use of evidence to make policy. *British Politics*, 141, pp.1–22.

Campbell, M., Dawkins, B., Fergie, G., Jung, A.-S., Lewis, R., McDaid, L., Olsen, J.R., Pollack, R., Rigby, B.P., Robinson, M., Skivington, K., Thomson, M. and Pearce, A., (2025) Commonly cited approaches to reducing health inequalities: a call for more clarity around their definition and underlying assumptions. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, p.jech-2025-224952.

Carrigan, M., Szmigin, I. and Leek, S., (2006) Managing routine food choices in UK families: The role of convenience consumption. *Appetite*, 473, pp.372–383.

Caruso, O.T., McEachern, L.W., Minaker, L.M. and Gilliland, J.A., (2024) The Influence of the School Neighborhood Food Retail Environment on Unhealthy Food Purchasing Behaviors Among Adolescents: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior*, 563, pp.145–161.

Castelo, A.F.M., Schäfer, M. and Silva, M.E., (2021) Food practices as part of daily routines: A conceptual framework for analysing networks of practices. *Appetite*, 157, p.104978.

Chang, M., Green, L. and Petrokofsky, C., (2022) *Public Health Spatial Planning in Practice*. [online] Bristol, UK: Policy Press. Available at:

<https://policy.bristoluniversitypress.co.uk/public-health-spatial-planning-in-practice>
[Accessed 29 Jan. 2026].

Cohen, P.N., (1998) Replacing housework in the service economy: Gender, Class, and Race-Ethnicity in Service Spending. *Gender & Society*, 122, pp.219–231.

Cohn, S., (2014) From Health Behaviours to Health Practices: An Introduction. In: *From Health Behaviours to Health Practices*. [online] John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp.1–6. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118898345.ch1> [Accessed 8 Oct. 2025].

Daniel, C., (2020) Is healthy eating too expensive?: How low-income parents evaluate the cost of food. *Social Science & Medicine*, 248, p.112823.

Davis, B.A., (2020) Discrimination: A Social Determinant Of Health Inequities. *Health Affairs Forefront*. [online] Available at: <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/10.1377/forefront.20200220.518458/full/> [Accessed 8 Jan. 2026].

Dazeley, P. and Houston-Price, C., (2015) Exposure to foods' non-taste sensory properties. A nursery intervention to increase children's willingness to try fruit and vegetables. *Appetite*, 84, pp.1–6.

DEFRA, (2024) *United Kingdom Food Security Report*. [Official Statistics] London (UK): UK Parliament. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/united-kingdom-food-security-report-2024> [Accessed 28 May 2025].

DEFRA, (2025a) *A UK government food strategy for England, considering the wider UK food system*. [Policy Paper] Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs: HM Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/a-uk-government-food-strategy-for-england/a-uk-government-food-strategy-for-england-considering-the-wider-uk-food-system> [Accessed 1 Feb. 2026].

DEFRA, (2025b) *Leading food experts join Government food strategy to restore pride in British food*. [Press release] GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/leading-food-experts-join-government-food-strategy-to-restore-pride-in-british-food> [Accessed 2 Feb. 2026].

Delormier, T., Frohlich, K.L. and Potvin, L., (2009) Food and eating as social practice – understanding eating patterns as social phenomena and implications for public health. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 312, pp.215–228.

Department of Health, (2022) *Statutory guidance on joint strategic needs assessments and joint health and wellbeing strategies*. London (UK): UK Government.

Devine, C.M., Jastran, M., Jabs, J., Wethington, E., Farell, T.J. and Bisogni, C.A., (2006) “A lot of sacrifices:” Work–family spillover and the food choice coping strategies of low-wage employed parents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 6310, pp.2591–2603.

DHSC, (2026) *Landmark junk food ad ban to protect kids' health*. [Press Release] GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/landmark-junk-food-ad-ban-to-protect-kids-health> [Accessed 1 Feb. 2026].

Dimbleby, H., (2021) *National Food Strategy - The Plan*. [Independent Review] Available at: <https://www.nationalfoodstrategy.org/> [Accessed 3 Jan. 2026].

Doherty, B., Jackson, P., Poppy, G.M., Wagstaff, C. and White, M., (2022) UK government food strategy lacks ambition to achieve transformative food system change. *Nature Food*, 37, pp.481–482.

Duarte, C., Matos, M., Stubbs, R.J., Gale, C., Morris, L., Gouveia, J.P. and Gilbert, P., (2017) The Impact of Shame, Self-Criticism and Social Rank on Eating Behaviours in Overweight and Obese Women Participating in a Weight Management Programme. *PLoS ONE*, 121, p.e0167571.

DWP, (2026) *£1 billion resilience fund and next step towards removal of two-child limit provide safety net for families*. [online] GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/1-billion-resilience-fund-and-next-step-towards-removal-of-two-child-limit-provide-safety-net-for-families> [Accessed 10 Mar. 2026].

EFRA, (2023) *Food Security*. [House of Commons Committee report] London (UK): UK Parliament. Available at: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmenvfru/622/report.html#footnote-176> [Accessed 27 May 2025].

Evans, R., Christiansen, P., Bateson, M., Nettle, D., Keenan, G.S. and Hardman, C.A., (2025) Understanding the association between household food insecurity and diet quality: The role of psychological distress, food choice motives and meal patterning. *Appetite*, 212, p.108007.

FAO, (2019) *The state of food security and nutrition in the world: safeguarding against economic slowdowns and downturns*. part of THE STATE OF THE WORLD series. [online] Rome: the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Available at: <https://www.wfp.org/publications/2019-state-food-security-and-nutrition-world-sofi-safeguarding-against-economic> [Accessed 3 Jan. 2021].

FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP, and WHO, (2025) *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2025. Addressing high food price inflation for food security and nutrition*. The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World (SOFI). [online] Rome, Italy: FAO; IFAD; UNICEF; WFP; WHO. Available at: <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/cd6008en> [Accessed 26 Oct. 2025].

Fielding-Singh, P. and Oleschuk, M., (2023) Unequal foodwork: Situating the sociology of feeding within diet and nutrition disparities. *Sociology Compass*, 174, p.e13067.

Food Foundation, (2025) *The Broken Plate: At a glance*. [online] London. Available at: <https://foodfoundation.org.uk/publication/broken-plate-2025> [Accessed 23 Jan. 2026].

Food Standards Agency, (2022) *Chapter 1: The nation's plate, our diet and food choices today*. [Our Food 2021: An annual review of food standards across the UK] Available at: <https://www.food.gov.uk/our-work/chapter-1-the-nations-plate-our-diet-and-food-choices-today> [Accessed 23 Jan. 2026].

Foodrise, (2025) *Used by: How businesses dump their waste on food charities*. London (UK).

Gardiner, B.H., Hickson, M., Haslam-Lucas, A., Diouri, B., Ruminska, J., Dunn, L., Ashton, Y., Hunt, L.S. and Pettinger, C., (2026a) Transforming urban food systems: could food democracy and food citizenship be advanced by personal and community impacts of co-production processes? *Environmental Research: Food Systems*. [online] Available at: <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2976-601X/ae69ea> [Accessed 8 May 2026].

Gardiner, B.H., Roughton, M., Howard, L., Hunt, L., Nisa, U. and Pettinger, C., (2026b) Delivering participatory food systems research in our own communities: reflections about co-production by community food researchers and community partners. *Research for All*, [online] 101. Available at: <https://journals.uclpress.co.uk/r4a/article/id/3838/> [Accessed 4 June 2026].

Gibbs, L. and Mutebi, N., (2026) *Trust, public engagement and UK Parliament*. [online] London (UK): UK Parliament. Available at: <https://post.parliament.uk/research-briefings/post-pb-0066/> [Accessed 2 Feb. 2026].

Goddard, J., (2025) 'A plan to fix our broken food system': House of Lords Food, Diet and Obesity Committee report. [online] Available at: <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/a-plan-to-fix-our-broken-food-system-house-of-lords-food-diet-and-obesity-committee-report/> [Accessed 2 Apr. 2026].

Griffin, N., Phillips, S.M., Hillier-Brown, F., Wistow, J., Fairbrother, H., Holding, E., Powell, K. and Summerbell, C., (2021) A critique of the English national policy from a social determinants of health perspective using a realist and problem representation approach: the 'Childhood Obesity: a plan for action' (2016, 2018, 2019). *BMC Public Health*, 211, p.2284.

Halkier, B. and Holm, L., (2021) Linking socioeconomic disadvantage to healthiness of food practices: Can a practice-theoretical perspective sharpen everyday life analysis? *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 433, pp.750–763.

Hankivsky, O. and Christoffersen, A., (2008) Intersectionality and the determinants of health: a Canadian perspective. *Critical Public Health*, 183, pp.271–283.

Harari, D., (2024) *Low growth: The economy's biggest challenge*. [online] UK Parliament: House of Commons Library. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/low-growth-the-economys-biggest-challenge/> [Accessed 28 Jan. 2026].

Hasenböhler, A., Javaux, G., Payen de la Garanderie, M., Szabo de Edelenyi, F., Bourhis, L., Agaësse, C., De Sa, A., Huybrechts, I., Pierre, F., Coumoul, X., Julia, C., Kesse-Guyot, E., Allès, B., Fezeu, L.K., Hercberg, S., Deschasaux-Tanguy, M., Cosson, E., Tatulashvili, S., Chassaing, B., Srour, B. and Touvier, M., (2026) Associations between preservative food additives and type

2 diabetes incidence in the NutriNet-Santé prospective cohort. *Nature Communications*, 161, p.11199.

Hawkes, C., Gallagher-Squires, C., Spires, M., Hawkins, N., Neve, K., Brock, J., Isaacs, A., Parrish, S. and Coleman, P., (2024) The full picture of people's realities must be considered to deliver better diets for all. *Nature Food*, 511, pp.894–900.

Health Foundation, (2026) *Health Foundation response to the junk food advertising ban*. [Press Release] Available at: <https://www.health.org.uk/press-office/press-releases/health-foundation-response-to-the-junk-food-advertising-ban> [Accessed 1 Feb. 2026].

Heaton, J., (2012) Types of Qualitative Secondary Analysis. In: J. Goodwin, ed., *SAGE Secondary Data Analysis*. [online] SAGE Publications Ltd, pp.v3-290. Available at: <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/edvol/sage-secondary-data-analysis/chpt/types-qualitative-secondary-analysis> [Accessed 3 Nov. 2025].

Hirth, S., Boons, F. and Doherty, B., (2021) Unpacking food to go: Packaging and food waste of on the go provisioning practices in the UK. *Geoforum*, 126, pp.115–125.

Hodder, R.K., O'Brien, K.M., Wyse, R.J., Tzelepis, F., Yoong, S., Stacey, F.G. and Wolfenden, L., (2024) Interventions for increasing fruit and vegetable consumption in children aged five years and under. [online] 9. Available at: <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD008552.pub8/full> [Accessed 26 May 2026].

Holley, C.E., Farrow, C. and Haycraft, E., (2017) A Systematic Review of Methods for Increasing Vegetable Consumption in Early Childhood. *Current Nutrition Reports*, 62, pp.157–170.

Horton, P., Gill, M. and Poppy, G., (2025) Food systems transformation: rationale and methodologies. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 3801935, p.20240146.

Hunt, L., Pettinger, C. and Wagstaff, C., (2023) A critical exploration of the diets of UK disadvantaged communities to inform food systems transformation: a scoping review of qualitative literature using a social practice theory lens. *BMC Public Health*, 231, p.1970.

Hunter, E., Stone, R.A., Brown, A., Hardman, C.A., Johnstone, A.M., Greatwood, H.C., Dineva, M. and Douglas, F., (2025) "We go hunting ...": Understanding experiences of people living with obesity and food insecurity when shopping for food in the supermarket to meet their weight related goals. *Appetite*, 205, p.107794.

Inglis, G., Jenkins, P., McHardy, F., Sosu, E. and Wilson, C., (2023) Poverty stigma, mental health, and well-being: A rapid review and synthesis of quantitative and qualitative research. *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology*, 334, pp.783–806.

Irwin, S., (2013) Qualitative secondary data analysis: Ethics, epistemology and context. *Progress in Development Studies*, 134, pp.295–306.

- Isaacs, A., Halligan, J., Neve, K. and Hawkes, C., (2022) From healthy food environments to healthy wellbeing environments: Policy insights from a focused ethnography with low-income parents' in England. *Health & Place*, 77, p.102862.
- Jabs, J. and Devine, C.M., (2006) Time scarcity and food choices: An overview. *Appetite*, 472, pp.196–204.
- Jackson, P. and Viehoff, V., (2016) Reframing convenience food. *Appetite*, 98, pp.1–11.
- Jackson, T., (2024) *The False Economy of Big Food*. [online] Food, Farming and Countryside Commission. Available at: <https://ffcc.co.uk/publications/the-false-economy-of-big-food> [Accessed 23 Jan. 2026].
- Kahryn Hughes, (2023) *Qualitative Secondary Analysis – an introduction*. [online] National Centre for Research Methods online learning resource. Available at: <https://www.ncrm.ac.uk> [Accessed 3 Nov. 2025].
- van Kesteren, R. and Evans, A., (2025) Hidden inequalities of ease: A practice-theoretical approach to understanding the links between social deprivation and diet. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 251, pp.3–27.
- Kinniburgh, M., (2025) *Could taxpayer-funded public diners be revived?* [online] BBC Scotland News. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cnvm299d5m1o> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].
- Laila, A., Leme, A.C., Hou, S., Ma, D.W.L. and Haines, J., (2023) Perceived challenges and strategies to achieve Canada's Food Guide recommendation to "Cook more often": Findings from parents of young children. *Appetite*, 182, p.106413.
- Landau-Czajka, A., (2002) Diet patterns in 19th-20th century school manuals. *Acta Poloniae Historica*, [online] 85. Available at: https://rcin.org.pl/ihpan/Content/14444/PDF/WA303_26298_2002-85_APH-12_o.pdf [Accessed 24 Dec. 2025].
- Leask, C.F., Sandlund, M., Skelton, D.A., Altenburg, T.M., Cardon, G., Chinapaw, M.J.M., De Bourdeaudhuij, I., Verloigne, M., Chastin, S.F.M. and on behalf of the GrandStand, S.S. and T.G. on the M.R.G., (2019) Framework, principles and recommendations for utilising participatory methodologies in the co-creation and evaluation of public health interventions. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 51, p.2.
- Lloyd-Evans, S. and Oenga, E., (2023) *Participatory Action Research: A Toolkit*. [online] Reading (UK): University of Reading. Available at: <https://research.reading.ac.uk/community-based-research/participatory-action-research-a-toolkit/> [Accessed 2 Dec. 2024].
- Lloyd-Evans, S. and the Whitley Researchers, (2021) Beyond coping: families and young people's journeys through austerity, relational poverty and stigma. In: *Austerity Across Europe: Living, Feeling and Experiencing Economic Crises*,. Abingdon (UK): Routledge.

Loopstra, R., (2018) Interventions to address household food insecurity in high-income countries. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 773, pp.270–281.

Loopstra, R., (2020) *Vulnerability to food insecurity since the COVID-19 lockdown: Preliminary Report*. London: Kings College London.

López Cifuentes, M. and Sonnino, R., (2024) Transforming the food environment: An assemblage-based research approach. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 52, p.100874.

Lucan, S.C., (2015) Concerning Limitations of Food-Environment Research: A Narrative Review and Commentary Framed around Obesity and Diet-Related Diseases in Youth. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 1152, pp.205–212.

Lumivero, (2023) *NVivo*. Available at: <https://lumivero.com/products/nvivo/> [Accessed 16 July 2025].

Lundberg, O., (2020) Next steps in the development of the social determinants of health approach: the need for a new narrative. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, 485, pp.473–479.

MacDonald, S., Murphy, S. and Elliott, E., (2018) Controlling food, controlling relationships: exploring the meanings and dynamics of family food practices through the diary-interview approach. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 405, pp.779–792.

Mallorie, S., (2024) The Relationship Between Poverty And NHS Services. [The King's Fund] *The King's Fund*. Available at: <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/insight-and-analysis/long-reads/relationship-poverty-nhs-services> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

Manchester Food Board, (n.d.) The Eatwell Guide and culturally appropriate food. Available at: <https://www.manchesterfoodboard.co.uk/blogs-new/the-eatwell-guide-a-discussion-on-culturally-appropriate-food> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

Marmot, M., Allen, J., Boyce, T., Goldblatt, P. and Morrison, J., (2020) *Marmot Review 10 Years On*. [online] Institute of Health Equity. Available at: <https://www.instituteofhealthequity.org/resources-reports/marmot-review-10-years-on> [Accessed 23 Jan. 2026].

Mattioni, D., Loconto, A.M. and Brunori, G., (2020) Healthy diets and the retail food environment: A sociological approach. *Health & Place*, 61, p.102244.

McCartney, G. and Popay, J., (2025) Are place-based approaches to reducing health inequalities a highway to success or a policy dead-end? *Journal of Critical Public Health*, 22, pp.39–50.

McCartney, G., Popham, F., McMaster, R. and Cumbers, A., (2019) Defining health and health inequalities. *Public Health*, 172, pp.22–30.

McGowan, V.J., Buckner, S., Mead, R., McGill, E., Ronzi, S., Beyer, F. and Bambra, C., (2021) Examining the effectiveness of place-based interventions to improve public health and reduce health inequalities: an umbrella review. *BMC Public Health*, 211, p.1888.

McMahon, N.E., (2022) Working 'upstream' to reduce social inequalities in health: a qualitative study of how partners in an applied health research collaboration interpret the metaphor. *Critical Public Health*, 325, pp.654–664.

McMahon, N.E., (2023) What shapes local health system actors' thinking and action on social inequalities in health? A meta-ethnography. *Social Theory & Health*, 212, pp.119–139.

MHCLG, (2015) *English indices of deprivation 2015*. [Accredited official statistics] London (UK): Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (2018 to 2021). Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2015> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

MHCLG, (2025) *English indices of deprivation 2025: statistical release*. [Accredited official statistics] London (UK): Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2025/english-indices-of-deprivation-2025-statistical-release> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

Mohd Nor, N.D., Houston-Price, C., Harvey, K. and Methven, L., (2021) The effects of taste sensitivity and repeated taste exposure on children's intake and liking of turnip (*Brassica rapa* subsp. *rapa*); a bitter *Brassica* vegetable. *Appetite*, 157, p.104991.

Moisio, R., Arnould, E.J. and Price, L.L., (2004) Between Mothers and Markets: Constructing family identity through homemade food. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 43, pp.361–384.

Motulsky, S.L., (2021) Is member checking the gold standard of quality in qualitative research? *Qualitative Psychology*, 83, pp.389–406.

Mudie, R., O'Brien, A., Signori, C. and Singh, T., (2025) *The Missing Links: Connecting disadvantaged neighbourhoods to new economic opportunities*. [online] Independent Commission on Neighbourhoods. Available at: <https://www.neighbourhoodscommission.org.uk/report/the-missing-links-connecting-disadvantaged-neighbourhoods-to-new-economic-opportunities/> [Accessed 10 Feb. 2026].

Neufeld, L.M., Andrade, E.B., Suleiman, A.B., Barker, M., Beal, T., Blum, L.S., Demmler, K.M., Dogra, S., Hardy-Johnson, P., Lahiri, A., Larson, N., Roberto, C.A., Rodríguez-Ramírez, S., Sethi, V., Shamah-Levy, T., Strömmer, S., Tumilowicz, A., Weller, S. and Zou, Z., (2022) Food choice in transition: adolescent autonomy, agency, and the food environment. *The Lancet*, 39910320, pp.185–197.

NIHR, (2021) *Reaching Out - a practical guide to being inclusive in public involvement in health research*. Lessons learnt from the NIHR Reaching Out programme April 2021. [online] Available at: <https://arc-nenc.nihr.ac.uk/resources/nihr-reaching-out-a-practical-guide-to-being-inclusive-in-public-involvement-in-health-research/> [Accessed 28 Jan. 2024].

O'Brien, B.C., Harris, I.B., Beckman, T.J., Reed, D.A. and Cook, D.A., (2014) Standards for Reporting Qualitative Research: A Synthesis of Recommendations. *Academic Medicine*, 899, p.1245.

O'Connell, R., Knight, A. and Brannen, J., (2015) Food austerity from an historical perspective: Making sense of 1950s Mass Observation data in the contemporary era. *Discover Society*. Available at: <https://archive.discoversociety.org/2015/01/03/food-austerity-from-an-historical-perspective-making-sense-of-1950s-mass-observation-data-in-the-contemporary-era/> [Accessed 7 Apr. 2026].

OHID, (2022) *Health disparities and health inequalities: applying All Our Health*. [Guidance] GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/health-disparities-and-health-inequalities-applying-all-our-health/health-disparities-and-health-inequalities-applying-all-our-health> [Accessed 4 Feb. 2026].

OHID, (2025) *Wider Determinants of Health: August 2025 update*. [Official Statistics] GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/wider-determinants-of-health-august-2025-update> [Accessed 3 Feb. 2026].

Orford, J., (2025) How We Justify High Economic Inequality: Blaming and Shaming and the Role of Culture, Mass Media, and the Educational System. In: J. Orford, ed., *The Psychology Of Economic Inequality: Six Reasons Why We Are Failing to Challenge Great Inequalities of Income and Wealth*. [online] Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, pp.139–166. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-85564-1_7 [Accessed 25 Oct. 2025].

Osei-Assibey, G., Dick, S., Macdiarmid, J., Semple, S., Reilly, J.J., Ellaway, A., Cowie, H. and McNeill, G., (2012) The influence of the food environment on overweight and obesity in young children: a systematic review. *BMJ Open*, 26, p.e001538.

Ostrom, E., (1978) Citizen Participation and Policing: What Do We Know? *Journal of Voluntary Action Research*, 71–2, pp.102–108.

Passidomo, C., (2013) Going 'Beyond Food': Confronting Structures of Injustice in Food Systems Research and Praxis. *Journal of Agriculture, Food Systems, and Community Development*, 34, pp.89–93.

Pemberton, S., Fahmy, E., Sutton, E. and Bell, K., (2016) Navigating the stigmatised identities of poverty in austere times: Resisting and responding to narratives of personal failure. *Critical Social Policy*, 361, pp.21–37.

Pestoff, V., Brandsen, T. and Verschuere, B., (2012) *New Public Governance, the Third Sector, and Co-Production*. Abingdon, Oxon ; New York, NY: Routledge.

Pettinger, C., Hunt, L., Gardiner, H., Garg, P., Howard, L. and Wagstaff, C., (2023) Engaging with 'less affluent' communities for food system transformation: a community food researcher model (FoodSEqual project). *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, pp.1–15.

Pfeiffer, C., Speck, M., Strassner, C., Pfeiffer, C., Speck, M. and Strassner, C., (2017) What Leads to Lunch—How Social Practices Impact (Non-)Sustainable Food Consumption/Eating

Habits. *Sustainability*, [online] 98. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/9/8/1437> [Accessed 7 Jan. 2026].

Pinto, T.G., Souza, D.V. de, Dedivitis, R.A., Renno, A.C.M., Ribeiro, D.A. and Salvadori, D.M.F., (2026) Cytogenotoxicity of food preservatives in mammalian cells: A systematic review. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 49, p.e20250137.

Plessz, M., Dubuisson-Quellier, S., Gojard, S. and Barrey, S., (2016) How consumption prescriptions affect food practices: Assessing the roles of household resources and life-course events. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 161, pp.101–123.

Popkin, B.M. and Ng, S.W., (2022) The nutrition transition to a stage of high obesity and noncommunicable disease prevalence dominated by ultra-processed foods is not inevitable. *Obesity Reviews*, 231, p.e13366.

Power, M., Pybus, K.J., Pickett, K.E. and Doherty, B., (2021) “The reality is that on Universal Credit I cannot provide the recommended amount of fresh fruit and vegetables per day for my children”: moving from a behavioural to a systemic understanding of food practices. *Emerald Open Research*, [online] 110. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EOR-10-2023-0007> [Accessed 29 Jan. 2026].

Puddephatt, J.-A., Keenan, G.S., Fielden, A., Reaves, D.L., Halford, J.C.G. and Hardman, C.A., (2020) ‘Eating to survive’: A qualitative analysis of factors influencing food choice and eating behaviour in a food-insecure population. *Appetite*, 147, p.104547.

Ravikumar, D., Spyreli, E., Woodside, J., McKinley, M. and Kelly, C., (2022) Parental perceptions of the food environment and their influence on food decisions among low-income families: a rapid review of qualitative evidence. *BMC Public Health*, 221, p.9.

Rayner, M., (2025) Is the Eatwell Guide still appropriate for the UK? *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, pp.1–7.

Reading Borough Council, (2025) *Berkshire Observatory – Reading – Welcome to the Reading Observatory*. [online] Available at: <https://reading.berkshireobservatory.co.uk/> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

Reutter, L.I., Harrison, M.J. and Neufeld, A., (2002) Public Support for Poverty-related Policies. *Canadian Journal of Public Health = Revue Canadienne de Santé Publique*, 934, pp.297–302.

Ridley, M., Rao, G., Schilbach, F. and Patel, V., (2020) Poverty, depression, and anxiety: Causal evidence and mechanisms. *Science*, 3706522, p.eaay0214.

Robertson, L., Bowman, N., Wilks, L., McKendrick, J.H. and Sinclair, S., (2025) What works to prevent and tackle poverty stigma? A rapid evidence review. [online] Available at: <https://www.povertyalliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/Poverty-stigma-RER-report-February-2026.pdf> [Accessed 10 Mar. 2026].

Romani, S., Grappi, S., Bagozzi, R.P. and Barone, A.M., (2018) Domestic food practices: A study of food management behaviors and the role of food preparation planning in reducing waste. *Appetite*, 121, pp.215–227.

Russell, C., (2019) Four modes of change: to, for, with, by. *Hindsight*, [online] 28, 1 Jan. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/38713222/FOUR_MODES_OF_CHANGE_TO_FOR_WITH_BY [Accessed 24 Sept. 2025].

Russell, C. and McKnight, J., (2022) *The Connected Community: Discovering the Health, Wealth, and Power of Neighbourhoods*. Oakland, CA: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Ryan, G.W. and Bernard, H.R., (2003) Techniques to Identify Themes. *Field Methods*, 151, pp.85–109.

Rylatt, L. and Cartwright, T., (2016) Parental feeding behaviour and motivations regarding pre-school age children: A thematic synthesis of qualitative studies. *Appetite*, 99, pp.285–297.

Sacks, G., Robinson, E. and Cameron, A.J., (2019) Issues in Measuring the Healthiness of Food Environments and Interpreting Relationships with Diet, Obesity and Related Health Outcomes. *Current Obesity Reports*, 82, pp.98–111.

Salvy, S.-J., de la Haye, K., Bowker, J.C. and Hermans, R.C.J., (2012) Influence of peers and friends on children's and adolescents' eating and activity behaviors. *Physiology & Behavior*, 1063, pp.369–378.

Sawyer, E.A., Bourlakis, M., Conrad, D. and Wagstaff, C., (2023) Impact pathways: unravelling the hybrid food supply chain – identifying the relationships and processes to drive change. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 447, pp.1310–1323.

Scheelbeek, P., Green, R., Hadida, G., Nájera Espinosa, S., Turner, G. and Phalkey, R., (2023) Chapter 9. Climate change and food supply. In: *Health Effects of Climate Change (HECC) in the UK: 2023 report*. [online] London, UK: UK Health Security Agency. Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/659ff76ee96df5000df844c3/HECC-report-2023-chapter-9-food-supply.pdf> [Accessed 2 Apr. 2026].

Scheelbeek, P., Green, R., Papier, K., Knuppel, A., Alae-Carew, C., Balkwill, A., Key, T.J., Beral, V. and Dangour, A.D., (2020) Health impacts and environmental footprints of diets that meet the Eatwell Guide recommendations: analyses of multiple UK studies. *BMJ Open*, 108, p.e037554.

Schreier, M., (2014) Chapter 12: Qualitative Content Analysis. In: U. Flick, ed., *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Analysis*. [online] 1 Oliver's Yard, 55 City Road, London EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Shove, E., Pantzar, M. and Watson, M., (2012) *The Dynamics of Social Practice: Everyday Life and How it Changes*. [online] Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Smith, D. and Thompson, C., (2022) *Food Deserts and Food Insecurity in the UK: Exploring Social Inequality*. [online] Oxford, UNITED KINGDOM: Taylor & Francis Group.

Sobal, J. and Bisogni, C.A., (2009) Constructing Food Choice Decisions. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 38suppl_1, pp.s37–s46.

Statista, (2020) *Frequency of food shopping trips by gender in the UK 2020*. [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1125763/frequency-of-food-shopping-trips-by-gender-uk/> [Accessed 10 Oct. 2022].

Stone, R.A., Brown, A., Douglas, F., Green, M.A., Hunter, E., Lonnie, M., Johnstone, A.M. and Hardman, C.A., (2024) The impact of the cost of living crisis and food insecurity on food purchasing behaviours and food preparation practices in people living with obesity. *Appetite*, 196, p.107255.

Story, M., Kaphingst, K.M., Robinson-O'Brien, R. and Glanz, K., (2008) Creating Healthy Food and Eating Environments: Policy and Environmental Approaches. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 29Volume 29, 2008, pp.253–272.

Sutton, E., Pemberton, S., Fahmy, E. and Tamiya, Y., (2014) Stigma, Shame and the Experience of Poverty in Japan and the United Kingdom. *Social Policy and Society*, 131, pp.143–154.

Tarman, G., (2025) Where are we now with the development of the UK Food Strategy, and what comes next? *Sustain*. Available at: <https://www.sustainweb.org/blogs/jun25-uk-food-strategy/> [Accessed 12 June 2026].

TFL, (2026) *Free and discounted travel*. [online] Transport for London. Available at: <https://www.tfl.gov.uk/fares/free-and-discounted-travel> [Accessed 10 Mar. 2026].

Tomlinson, P., Hewitt, S. and Blackshaw, N., (2013) Joining up health and planning: how Joint Strategic Needs Assessment (JSNA) can inform health and wellbeing strategies and spatial planning. *Perspectives in Public Health*, 1335, pp.254–262.

Tsochantaridou, A., Sergentanis, T.N., Grammatikopoulou, M.G., Merakou, K., Vassilakou, T. and Kornarou, E., (2023) Food Advertisement and Dietary Choices in Adolescents: An Overview of Recent Studies. *Children*, 103, p.442.

Tyler, I. and Campbell, S., (2024) *Poverty stigma: a glue that holds poverty in place*. [online] Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available at: <https://www.jrf.org.uk/power-and-participation/poverty-stigma-a-glue-that-holds-poverty-in-place> [Accessed 27 Jan. 2026].

UN, (2022) *SDG 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns - report*. [Statistics Division] New York (USA): United Nations. Available at: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/goal-12/> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2026].

Vaismoradi, M., Jones, J., Turunen, H. and Snelgrove, S., (2016) Theme development in qualitative content analysis and thematic analysis. *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 65, p.p100.

Vonthron, S., Perrin, C. and Soulard, C.-T., (2020) Foodscape: A scoping review and a research agenda for food security-related studies. *PLOS ONE*, 155, p.e0233218.

Vos, M., Deforche, B., Van Kerckhove, A., Michels, N., Poelman, M., Geuens, M. and Van Lippevelde, W., (2022) Determinants of healthy and sustainable food choices in parents with a higher and lower socioeconomic status: A qualitative study. *Appetite*, 178, p.106180.

Wagstaff, C., Pettinger, C., Relton, C., Psarikidou, K., Swan, E., Methven, L., Kuhnle, G., McCloy, R., Lloyd-Evans, S., Thomas, M., Puranik, M., Chadwick, M., Zischka, L., Smith, R., Gardiner, H., Hunt, L., Pan, J., Bradbeer, J., Sutton, R., Diouri, B., Williams, E., Alloune, L., Bennett, P., Howard, L., Garg, P., Ashton, Y., Hart, J., Miah, S., Hussein, S., Yip, J. and Taylor, S., (2025) Addressing food system determinants of health inequalities in urban environments: learnings from the FoodSEqual and FoodSEqual-Health projects. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 3801935, p.20240150.

Warde, A., (2014) After taste: Culture, consumption and theories of practice. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 143, pp.279–303.

Wickham, S., Bentley, L., Rose, T., Whitehead, M., Taylor-Robinson, D. and Barr, B., (2020) Effects on mental health of a UK welfare reform, Universal Credit: a longitudinal controlled study. *The Lancet Public Health*, 53, pp.e157–e164.

Wright-Pedersen, S., Vidgen, H. and Gallegos, D., (2026) Children's perspectives of their everyday food practices: insights to inform policy and interventions. *PLOS ONE*, 211, p.e0341234.

Zorbas, C., Jeyapalan, D., Nunez, V. and Backholer, K., (2023) Community lived experience should be central to food systems policy. *Nature Food*, 41, pp.7–9.